

Determining the Association of Post Defecation Cleaning Habit and STH infections among Orang Asli in Kg. Donglai Baru, Semenyih, Selangor.

^{1*}Alif Naim, M.; ¹Mehru Nisha; ²Fabian Davamani; ³Tong Woei Yenn

¹ Institute of Medical Science Technology, Universiti Kuala Lumpur (UniKL), A1-1, Jalan TKS 1, Taman Kajang Sentral, Selangor, 43000 Kajang, Selangor, Malaysia

² International Medical University (IMU), No.126, Jalan Jalil Perkasa 19, Bukit Jalil, 57000, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

³ Universiti Kuala Lumpur, Branch Campus Malaysian Institute of Chemical and Bioengineering Technology, Lot 1988 Kawasan Perindustrian Bandar Vendor, Taboh Naning, 78000 Alor Gajah, Melaka, Malaysia.

Corresponding Author: mehrunisha@unikl.edu.my

Introduction: Soil-transmitted helminth (STH) infections occurs via feco-oral route. World Health Organization (WHO) reported 90% of children from poor communities with inadequate hygiene and sanitation are prone to at least one STH infection. In Malaysia, Orang Asli (indigenous people) is the most predominant communities prone to get STH infections. Hence, this study was aimed to determine the association of defecation habits and STHs infections among Orang Asli in Kampong (Village) Donglai Baru, Semenyih, Selangor, Malaysia.

Methods: Survey based on questionnaires was conducted to gather information on the villagers which included post defecation and cleaning habit among the villagers. The stool samples were collected from volunteers and basic parasitology method like floatation technique was carried out to determine the type and burden of STHs.

Results: A total of thirty five (n=35) samples were collected, in which 85.7% (n=30) depicted *Trichuris trichiura* and 91.45% (n=32) was positive for *Ascaris lumbricoides*. Results were analysed using Chi-square test (SPSS version 22). We found that 60.0% of the villagers used stored water, 22.9% of them using river water, 8.6% for both using leaves and musolla toilet for cleaning after defecation. The Pearson Chi-squared association for defecation and cleaning using water storage was significant for *T. trichiura* ($p < 0.05$) but not for *A. lumbricoides* ($p = 0.06$)

Conclusion: It is recommended good hygiene practice after defecation to reduce STHs transmission.